

HIERARCHICAL SIMULATION OF STRENGTH AND DAMAGE ACCUMULATION IN FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES UNDER LONGITUDINAL TENSION

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ABSTRACT

This work proposes a numerical approach to model size effects on the stochastic longitudinal tensile strength of composite fibre bundles. A Monte-Carlo progressive failure analysis is implemented to calculate the strength distributions of hierarchical fibre bundles, which are formed by grouping a predefined number (coordination number) of smaller-order bundles into a larger-order bundle. This approach is firstly validated against an equivalent analytical model previously developed by the authors, which is restricted to the case of coordination number equal to two. The numerical approach is then applied to higher coordination numbers, thus extending the analysis to more realistic load-sharing configurations and making this approach suitable for the stochastic analysis of fibre-reinforced composites and the associated size effects.

1 INTRODUCTION

Statistical size effects govern the damage accumulation and failure of UniDirectional (UD) composites under longitudinal tension, and pose a challenge to use coupon-based experimental data for the design of large structures [1, 2]. Most authors agree that the statistics of fibre strength are essential for establishing the relationship between composite longitudinal tensile strength and size effects. Consequently, several modelling approaches have been suggested for the stochastic analysis of Fiber-Reinforced Polymers (FRPs) [1-3].

Fibre Bundle Models (FBMs) [4] accurately represent the physics involved in longitudinal tensile failure and the associated size effects. This type of model focuses on calculating the strength distribution of a bundle of n parallel fibres of a given characteristic length, and the Weakest Link Theory (WLT) [5] is then used to scale the result for a longer chain of bundles [6-8]. In general, the complexity of FBMs increases with the number of fibres (n) in the bundle's cross-section, and exact solutions are attainable for small bundles only.

However, self-similar or quasi-fractal fracture surfaces have been reported in UD laminas and fibre bundles [9,10], providing experimental evidence for a hierarchical failure process. Consequently, Pimenta and Pinho [11] recently proposed a hierarchical scaling law for the strength of composite fibre bundles, which has been extensively validated against experimental results and predicts full strength distributions for bundles of any size. As shown in Figure 1a, the model assumes that hierarchical bundles are formed by pairing two individual fibres (level-[0]) into a level-[1] bundle, and sequentially grouping two level-[i] bundles into one level-[$i + 1$] bundle (i.e., using a *coordination*

number $c = 2$). Once a level- $[i]$ bundle is broken, stresses are recovered according to a plastic shear-lag model, so that linear stress concentrations apply within a characteristic length which is a function of both the applied load and the number of broken fibres. Although this approach leads to an efficient computation of bundle strength distributions, imposing a coordination number $c = 2$ results in very high stress concentrations in the proximity of fibre breaks.

The objective of the present work is therefore to extend Pimenta and Pinho's model to more realistic load-sharing configurations, generalising the hierarchical approach to higher coordination numbers c (Figure 1b) and, consequently, reducing stress concentration factors in the neighbourhood of fibre breaks. However, at higher c 's the increasing number of possible sequences of failure events in a bundle complicates the analytical evaluation of its strength distribution and, therefore, a new numerical approach is needed. In this work, a Monte-Carlo progressive failure analysis is proposed to calculate the bundle strength distributions, where the failure events are simulated through a discrete representation of hierarchical bundles (i.e., a level- $[i]$ bundle is discretised into smaller bundles of level $[i - 1]$).

Figure 1: a) First 4 bundle levels with coordination number $c = 2$;
b) Fibre arrangements for different coordination numbers.

This paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents a brief overview of the hierarchical analytical model [11], providing the basis for the numerical implementation in Section 3. Results of the proposed numerical model are shown in Section 4, and pros and cons are discussed in Section 5. Finally, the main conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2 OVERVIEW OF THE HIERARCHICAL ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR COMPOSITE FIBRE BUNDLES

Consider a level- $[1]$ bundle composed by two level- $[0]$ fibres (A and B , Figure 2), and assume the far field stress σ^∞ progressively increasing until a first break occurs in the middle of fibre A . Based on a perfectly-plastic shear-lag model, the failed fibre A recovers the remote stress σ^∞ within the level- $[0]$ effective recovery length, i.e.

$$l_e^{[0]}(\sigma^\infty) = 2 \cdot \frac{A^f}{C^{[0]} \cdot \tau_{SL}} \cdot \sigma^\infty, \quad (1)$$

where A^f is the cross-sectional area of a single fibre, τ_{SL} is the matrix/interface yield stress in shear, and $C^{[0]}$ is the perimeter of the level- $[0]$ shear-lag boundary, at which shear stresses can be transferred

[11]. From equilibrium, a linear stress concentration applies to fibre *B*, which reaches a stress concentration factor $k = 2$ in the proximity of the fibre break ($x = 0$). Bundle failure requires fibre *B* to fail nearby the break in fibre *A*, so as to promote complete yielding of the matrix/interface between the two fibre-breaks (Figure 2). Therefore, once fibre *A* fails, the level-[1] *control region* is defined as the region where a break in fibre *B* would lead to bundle failure, i.e.

$$l_c^{[1]}(\sigma^\infty) = 2 \cdot l_e^{[0]}(\sigma^\infty). \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: Definition of the critical distance between fibre breaks: the bundle fails only if fibre *B* breaks at a distance smaller than $l_c/2 = l_e$ from the break in fibre *A* [11].

As illustrated in Figure 3, the control region is partitioned into 4 segments (A_1 , A_2 , B_1 and B_2) of equal length $l_e^{[0]}$, and two assumptions are made:

- A(i)* The bundle is represented by a chain of independent control regions (which neglects bundle-ends effects by shifting the first fibre-break to the centre of the control region);
- A(ii)* Within a control region, each fibre can fail only once (to guarantee simple stress fields as those presented in Figure 2).

Figure 3: Definition of the control region and fibre segments in a level-[1] bundle [11].

Based on the assumptions above, the list of sequences of events leading to bundle failure is defined as follows:

- E_1 : failure of segment A_1 and unstable failure (with no increase of the far-field stress) of segment B_1 due to stress concentrations;
- E_2 : failure of segment A_1 and stable failure (after incrementing σ^∞) of segment B_1 due to stress concentrations;
- E_3 : failure of segment A_1 and stable failure of segment B_2 due to independent fibre flaws (including

growth and coalescence of matrix damage between fibre breaks).

Consequently, the total failure probability of the bundle is given by the union of events E_1 , E_2 and E_3 , which yields the following expression for the level-[1] bundle survival probability under uniform stress σ^∞ within the control length $l_c^{[1]}$:

$$S_{U,c}^{[1]}(\sigma^\infty) = S_{U,e}^{[0]}(\sigma^\infty)^4 + 2 \cdot \left[1 - S_{U,e}^{[0]}(\sigma^\infty)^2\right] \cdot S_{U,e}^{[0]}(\sigma^\infty) \cdot S_{K,e}^{[0]}(\sigma^\infty), \quad (3)$$

where $S_{U,e}^{[0]}$ and $S_{K,e}^{[0]}$ are the survival probability of a single-fibre segment of length $l_e^{[0]}$, and the subscripts U and K respectively refer to a uniform stress loading (σ^∞) and a linear stress profile with concentration factor $k = 2$. The level-[1] bundle strength distribution is then obtained as the complement of the level-[1] bundle survival probability, i.e. $F_{U,c}^{[1]}(\sigma^\infty) = 1 - S_{U,c}^{[1]}(\sigma^\infty)$.

Equation (3) relates the strength distribution of the level-[1] bundle to that of a single fibre, for which a Weibull distribution is used in [11]. Assuming a hierarchical failure process, Equation (3) is finally extended to any bundle level, so that the following recursive formula is provided:

$$S_{U,c}^{[i+1]}(\sigma^\infty) = S_{U,e}^{[i]}(\sigma^\infty)^4 + 2 \cdot \left[1 - S_{U,e}^{[i]}(\sigma^\infty)^2\right] \cdot S_{U,e}^{[i]}(\sigma^\infty) \cdot S_{K,e}^{[i]}(\sigma^\infty), \quad (4)$$

in which the control length and the recovery length scale hierarchically too, as reported in [11]. It should be noted that the first term on the right-hand side of Equation (4) corresponds to the WLT, and the second term accounts for the survivability of the level-[$i + 1$] bundle once one of the level-[i] bundles fails. The WLT is used within any bundle level to scale the strength distribution for a different length.

3 NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Simulation of failure events in a bundle with 2 fibres

The analytical hierarchical model introduced in the previous section is here reformulated using a discrete representation of fibres and bundles. Consider first a level-[1] bundle of length $L^{[1]}$ and coordination number $c = 2$ (i.e. a 2-fibres bundle as represented in Figure 2), in which each fibre is discretised into a large number of level-[0] elements of equal length $\Delta^{[0]}$. A value of strength is then generated for each fibre-element (Figure 4a), based on a random sampling of level-[0] strength distribution. A Weibull distribution is assumed for the individual fibres (for consistency with the analytical model [11]); being l_r the reference length at which the Weibull distribution was measured, the distribution used in the model is then scaled to the element length $\Delta^{[0]}$ by applying the WLT,

$$F_{U,\Delta^{[0]}}^{[0]}(\sigma^\infty) = 1 - \left[1 - F_{U,l_r}^{[0]}(\sigma^\infty)\right]^{\Delta^{[0]}/l_r}, \quad (5)$$

where $F_{U,l_r}^{[0]}$ and $F_{U,\Delta^{[0]}}^{[0]}$ denote the Weibull distribution at length l_r and $\Delta^{[0]}$, respectively. Finally, the element strengths are generated by inverse transform sampling method [12] applied to the level-[0] strength distribution, $F_{U,\Delta^{[0]}}^{[0]}$.

Figure 4a illustrates a situation where the applied stress σ^∞ overcomes the strength of elements 6 and 8 of fibre A, and of element 15 of fibre B, thus leading to local failures (highlighted in red colour). The corresponding stress field is shown in Figure 4b, which satisfies the equilibrium equation

$$\sigma_{A,j} + \sigma_{B,j} = 2\sigma^\infty, \quad (6)$$

where the stresses $\sigma_{A,j}$ and $\sigma_{B,j}$ are evaluated at the centre j -th element of fibre A and B, respectively.

Figure 4: a) Elements 6 and 8 of fibre A and element 15 of fibre B fail under the uniform stress σ^∞ ; b) Resulting stress fields with recovery regions in red and stress concentrations in green.

As shown in Figure 4b, the resulting stress fields can be more complex than those assumed in the analytical model (Figure 2). This is because the numerical implementation does not involve assumptions $A(i)$ and $A(ii)$, and the recovery regions can be here defined by superimposition of multiple stress-recovery fields (e.g., recovery region 1 in Figure 4b).

However, the proposed implementation preserves the basic sequences of events leading to bundle failure, i.e. E_1 , E_2 and E_3 defined in Section 2. This result is achieved by means of a progressive failure analysis, where the far field stress σ^∞ is increased starting from the strength value of the weakest element (at which the first local failure occurs), up to the termination of the analysis once a global failure of the bundle is detected. This global failure occurs when a recovery region in one fibre overlaps at least one recovery region in the other fibre, so that the equilibrium Equation (6) cannot be satisfied. At that point, the value of the far field stress σ^∞ is stored as an outcome of the stochastic level-[1] bundle strength, $X_{U,L[1]}^{[1]}$. The corresponding distribution $F_{U,L[1]}^{[1]}$ is obtained by a Monte-Carlo analysis, repeating the progressive failure analysis N times, each time randomly sampling the element strengths from the given individual fibre strength distribution.

3.2 Simulation of larger bundles and asymptotic analysis of the strength distribution

The resulting level-[1] strength distribution is subsequently used to sample the strengths of level-[1] elements in the simulation of a level-[2] bundle (Figure 5). As in the previous level, the WLT is used for length scaling, so that the level-[1] bundle distribution can be evaluated at the element length $\Delta^{[1]}$:

$$F_{U,\Delta^{[1]}}^{[1]}(\sigma^\infty) = 1 - \left[1 - F_{U,L[1]}^{[1]}(\sigma^\infty)\right]^{\Delta^{[1]}/L^{[1]}}. \quad (7)$$

Figure 5: The WLT is applied to scale the bundle distribution from the full level-[1] bundle length ($L^{[1]}$) to the level-[1] element length ($\Delta^{[1]}$), so that the level-[1] element strengths can be sampled for the analysis of the level-[2] bundle.

However, the accuracy of $F_{U,L^{[1]}}^{[1]}$ is limited by the finite number of Monte-Carlo analyses (N), as the right tail of $F_{U,L^{[1]}}^{[1]}$ above the $(1 - 1/N)$ -th quantile is unavoidably rounded up to 1. Consequently, the small ratio $\Delta^{[1]}/L^{[1]}$ in Equation 7 leads to the complete loss of a large portion of $F_{U,\Delta^{[1]}}^{[1]}$ (segment A-C in Figure 6), making it impossible to sample values for the element strength $X_{U,\Delta^{[1]}}^{[1]}$.

Figure 6: a) The limited number of Monte-Carlo analyses rounds up to 1 the right tail of both the bundle strength ($F_{U,L^{[1]}}^{[1]}$, blue curve) and the element strength ($F_{U,\Delta^{[1]}}^{[1]}$, black curve) distributions; the latter is fitted with the asymptotic distribution ($\lim_{\sigma^\infty \rightarrow \infty} F_{U,\Delta^{[1]}}^{[1]}(\sigma^\infty)$, red curve) provided by the WLT applied to the previous level bundle (Equation 8); b) region from plot a) highlighted.

This problem is circumvented by means of an asymptotic approximation of the bundle strength distributions. Since the Right Tail Asymptote (RTA) falls into the domain of large stresses σ^∞ , its shape is governed by unstable bundle failure due to stress concentrations (i.e., event E_1). In other words, the asymptotical strength of the level-[i] bundle is determined by the strength of its weakest sub-bundle of level [$i - 1$]. Such consideration is consistent with the WLT applied to the previous-level bundle, so that the following expression of the RTA is obtained:

$$\lim_{\sigma^\infty \rightarrow \infty} F_{U,\Delta^{[i]}}^{[i]}(\sigma^\infty) = 1 - \left[1 - F_{U,\Delta^{[i-1]}}^{[i-1]}(\sigma^\infty)\right]^c, \quad (8)$$

being c the coordination number. Therefore, Equation (8) is used to fit $F_{U,\Delta^{[1]}}^{[1]}$ (by letting $i = 1$, and $c = 2$ in this particular case), which will then be defined by the curve O-A-B-D (Figure 6); in the

numerical implementation, a tolerance is established for the residual gap $A-B$, which can be further reduced by increasing the ratio $\Delta^{[1]}/L^{[1]}$ to a value closer to the unit.

3.3 Extension of the numerical model to higher coordination numbers

Figure 7a illustrates the case of a level-[1] bundle with coordination number $c = 3$, where local failures affect elements 4 and 15 of fibre A , elements 8 and 12 of fibre B , and element 14 of fibre C . Figure 7b shows the corresponding stress field, which is calculated assuming the stress concentration to be equally distributed among intact elements. Therefore, indicating with $\sigma_{i,j}$ the value of stress evaluated at the j -th element of the i -th fibre it can be shown that

$$\sigma_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{l_e^{[0]}}{2 \cdot \sigma^\infty} \right) \cdot d_{i,j} & \text{if } j \in r_i \\ \sigma^\infty + \left[(c-1) \cdot \sigma^\infty - \sum_{h \neq i} \sigma_{h,j} \right] / \left(c - \sum_{h \neq i} b_{h,j} \right) & \text{if } j \notin r_i \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where $d_{i,j}$ is the positive distance from the j -th element of the i -th fibre to the closest broken element in the recovery region r_i (more than one element can fail within the same recovery region, e.g. recovery regions 1 and 2 in Figure 7b); and $b_{h,j}$ is a logic operator, which is 1 if the j -th element of the h -th fibre belongs to r_j and 0 otherwise.

Figure 7: a) Elements 4 and 15 of fibre A , elements 8 and 12 of fibre B , and element 14 of fibre C fail under uniform stress loading σ^∞ ;
b) The whole bundle fails due to non-equilibrium in elements 13 and 14 (dashed areas).

In order to extend the Monte-Carlo progressive failure analysis to higher c 's, it is here assumed that a global bundle failure occurs when all sub-bundles are broken and all recovery regions overlap in at least one element (e.g., elements $j = 13$ and $j = 14$ in Figure 7b). When this statement is true, the equilibrium cannot be satisfied, i.e.

$$\exists j: \sum_{i=1}^c \sigma_{i,j} < c \cdot \sigma^\infty . \quad (10)$$

4 RESULTS

4.1 Inputs and outputs

Table 1 presents the list of nominal input parameters of the hypothetical material considered in the original analytical model [11]. The first four parameters refer to the Weibull distribution for the strength of individual fibres, being X_m^f the mean value and CoV^f the coefficient of variation, while σ_0^f and m are respectively the scale and the shape parameters. Finally, τ_{SL} is the matrix/interface yield stress, ϕ^f the fibre diameter, V^f the fibre volume fraction, and l_r is the reference length for the scale parameter σ_0^f . The progressive failure analysis is repeated $N = 10^6$ times during the Monte-Carlo simulation, and the values of element and bundle lengths is optimised at each level, so as to use the minimum number of elements which guarantees accuracy and convergence of the output strength distribution.

Table 1: Input parameters for the numerical implementation.

Mechanical properties					Geometry		
X_m^f (GPa)	CoV^f (%)	σ_0^f (GPa)	m (—)	τ_{SL} (MPa)	ϕ^f (μm)	V^f (%)	l_r (mm)
4.5	25	4.93	4.54	70	5	60	10

4.2 Comparison between Monte-Carlo analysis and analytical model

Figure 8 illustrates the bundle strength distributions for $c = 2$ and a specimen length of 10 mm. The simulated strengths (full lines) show good agreement with Pimenta and Pinho's [11] model (dashed lines), proving that the numerical simulation correctly models the same features as the analytical one.

Figure 8: Simulated bundle strength distributions compared to Pimenta and Pinho's [11] model.

4.3 Effect of coordination number

Figure 9 evidences size effects on the statistics of the strength distributions, where the value of c is set equal to 2 and 3. Both the mean value and the CoV of the strength exhibit common behaviours at

different c 's: after an initial strengthening and steep reduction in variability, both the mean value and the variability of tensile strength gradually decrease with increasing specimen cross-section. In particular, for all c 's, the magnitude of size effects starts decreasing for bundle levels higher than 3, as indicated by the upwards curvature of the right tail of the curves in Figure 9a.

As the coordination number c increases, the curves in Figure 9 shift to higher mean strengths and lower CoVs. This strengthening effect is due to lower average stress concentration factors among intact fibres (or sub-bundles) in the proximity of fibre breaks (e.g., $k = 2$ and $k = 1.5$ are respectively applied for $c = 2$ as shown in Figure 4b and $c = 3$ in Figure 7b).

Figure 9: Bundle strength size effects on the mean value (a) and on the CoV (b) for coordination numbers c equal to 2 and 3, and comparison with Pimenta and Pinho's [11] model.

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Limitations of the present model

Computational time and convergence to the exact solution are the key factors to consider when running Monte-Carlo progressive failure analysis. On the one hand, small ratios $\Delta^{[i-1]}/L^{[i]}$ must be used with low-level bundles (see Figure 5), where stable failure events (E_2 and E_3) are most likely to occur and need a finer discretisation of the fibres (or sub-bundles) to be accurately simulated. On the other hand, small ratios $\Delta^{[i-1]}/L^{[i]}$ compromise the RTA fitting (see Figure 6 and Equation 8) and lead to large data sets slowing down the computation. Optimal ratios $\Delta^{[i-1]}/L^{[i]}$ must then be established for each bundle level and for each set of mechanical and geometrical properties of the composite material.

Moreover, the analytical sequences of events leading to bundle failure (E_1 , E_2 and E_2) are here collected into only one exhaustive global failure criterion, which is defined by the inequality in Equation 10. Such criterion may result in very high peaks in the stress profile as in the case of fibres A and B in Figure 7b while, in reality, the matrix would not be able to transfer stresses so effectively without failing. Therefore, the present numerical approach leads to an overestimation of the strength for high values of the coordination number c , and developing a new global failure criterion would increase accuracy and reduce the gap between the curves in Figure 9.

5.2 Advantages of the present model

The numerical model copes with more complex stress fields (see Figure 4b) than the analytical model [11] (see Figure 2), and there is no need to define a control region – and, consequently, no need

to impose assumptions $A(i)$ and $A(ii)$ (see Section 2) in the former. Therefore, the good agreement between analytical and numerical results in Figure 8 suggests that the predictions of the analytical model are not affected by these restrictions on the control region.

The arbitrariness of the stress profiles also allows the present analysis to be easily generalised to any value of the coordination number c . Therefore, the coordination number is treated as free parameter, and no modifications are made to the numerical implementation when dealing with different load-sharing configurations.

Finally, a user-defined input distribution (i.e., not necessarily a Weibull) can be used for the individual fibre strength. For instance, a bi-modal Weibull strength distribution has been proposed [13] to account for the effects of two different flaw populations in the fibres, one operating at longer gauge lengths and characterised by large variability, and another operating at shorter gauge lengths and associated with smaller strength variability. Such distribution could be introduced in the present implementation to further investigate the stochastic behaviour of fibre-reinforced composites and the related size effects.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A new numerical approach was developed to model size effects on the stochastic longitudinal tensile strength of composite fibre bundles. The method applies a discretisation of hierarchical bundles by grouping chains of level- $[i]$ bundles into a level- $[i + 1]$ bundle, and a Monte-Carlo progressive failure analysis evaluates the corresponding strength distribution. A comparison was carried out with the analytical model developed by Pimenta and Pinho [11] for the simple case of coordination number $c = 2$ (i.e., grouping fibres and bundles 2 by 2); the good agreement of the results proved that the numerical simulation represents the same features of the analytical model. Furthermore, the numerical method was generalised to any value of the coordination number c , and a strengthening effect was observed for increasing values of c , which can be explained by lower average stress concentration factors among intact fibres in the proximity of fibre breaks. Work is still underway to improve the final failure criterion and to further extend this method to the analysis of damage accumulation into clusters of fibre breaks, and results will be validated against experimental data.

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